

THE PHARMACEUTICAL COMPOUNDS INVESTIGATION AT THE RIVER BANK FILTRATION SITE LOCATED IN THE WARTA RIVER VALLEY (POLAND) – PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Krzysztof Dragon¹, Magdalena Matusiak¹, Marcin Siepak¹, Roksana Kruć-Fijałkowska¹,
Dariusz Drożdżyński², Marek Szczepański², Józef Górski¹

¹ - Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań, Institute of Geology, Hydrogeology and Water Protection Research Unit, Bogumiła Krygowskiego 12, 61-680 Poznań, Poland

² - Institute of Plant Protection-National Research Institute, Department of Pesticide Residue Research, Władysława Węgorka 20, 60-318 Poznań, Poland

ABSTRACT: *The contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) (e.g. pharmaceuticals, personal care products, drugs or pesticides) are increasingly detected in aquatic environments. The most apparent contamination source of river water pollution by pharmaceuticals is sewage treatment plants that discharge treated sewage effluent into the rivers. The river bank filtration systems (RBF) can effectively remove these contaminants from polluted river waters. The Śrem RBF site located in Warta River valley (Poland) was examined for pharmaceutical occurrence. The water samples for CECs investigation (114 substances) were taken from the river and four continuously pumped wells. Two wells located close to the river were chosen (40 and 45 m from the river), and two located at a greater distance (70 and 75 m from the river). This situation allows us to investigate the rate of pharmaceuticals removal along flow paths. The sum of pharmaceuticals concentration in the river water was 8151 ng/l. An apparent differentiation in the pharmaceutical removal rate was observed. The sum of pharmaceuticals concentration in wells is between 657 ng/l and 3290 ng/l. An evident decrease in pharmaceutical concentration is visible along flow lines. The reduction rate between the river and well VIII, located 45 m from the river, is 60 %, while between the river and well XIII, located 75 m from the river, the reduction rate is 75 %. For an explanation of the CECs spatial changeability, the groundwater flow model was constructed. The model made it possible to elucidate the knowledge of the RBF system well recharge conditions concerning the possibility of CECs contamination. It was proved that the volume of bank filtrate in individual wells represents the sum of interactions between aquifer lithology, riverbed morphology and the distance of the well from the river. The results also indicate that a higher CECs content in wells generally corresponds to a higher amount of river water in the well recharge and a shorter distance between the well and the river. The highest pharmaceutical totals occurred in wells characterised by the highest share of surface water, the shortest travel times and the highest leakage parameters, resulting mainly from the sandy homogeneous structure of the aquifer within its capture zones. On the contrary, the less permeable silty interbedding within the aquifer was likely to affect both the decrease in the efficiency of bank filtration and the lengthening of bank filtrate travel times, contributing to the growth of ambient groundwater in wells and the decrease in pharmaceutical concentration. This could be due to the screening effect of these low permeable interbedding and the dilution of bank filtrate due to the rising distance between the wells and the river. The research presented demonstrates the necessity of monitoring the CECs, especially in groundwater that can be strongly influenced by river water contamination (like RBF sites). This work has received funding from the National Science Centre of Poland (grant no. 2021/41/B/ST10/00094).*

Key words: pharmaceutical reduction rate, river bank filtration sites, groundwater flow model

